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Co-Patenting across European Innovation Systems (1980-2015): Methodological concerns and observed trends

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Introduction & Background

Innovation and technological progress have since long been acknowledged as vital for firms and as critical driving forces in enhancing societal progress and welfare. Within (national) innovation systems, a variety of sectors, such as firms, entrepreneurs, universities or public research organizations play important roles in advancing innovation efforts (Jacobides et al., 2018; Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1998; Lundvall, 1992). The notion of ‘open innovation’ (Chesbrough, 2003) highlights the trend towards a ‘division of innovation labour’, where firms increasingly engage in external collaborations – this however raise challenges related to the creation and capture of value among collaborating organizations.

In Chesbrough’s plea for open business models, the role of intellectual property (IP) rights is recognized as crucial for organizations to successfully leverage on the increasing ‘division of innovation labour’ (Chesbrough, 2006). Importantly, this involves not only developing and protecting knowledge among organizations, but also possibilities of buying, selling, licensing and transferring knowledge assets between organizations.

This broader view of openness in both organizational innovation efforts, as well as at the level of business models, complements ongoing debates about the general occurrence and success of R&D collaborations. Moreover, it extends the challenge of conceptually defining and empirically developing representative indicators, to not only capture joint ‘inventive’ efforts, but also other forms of joint ‘innovation’ activities.

Given the centrality of IP rights, considerable attention has been devoted to investigating patents, as they provide readily available information on some of these joint efforts. While the majority of recent work has considered co-inventorship as reflecting collaborative *invention* processes between different actors, another possibility of capturing joint *innovation* activities

resides in considering patents with multiple applicants, which are consequently co-owned by multiple assignees (Belderbos et al., 2014; Hagedoorn, 2003; Walsh et al., 2016).

While not all collaborations will result in patents (let alone, co-owned patents) it is nonetheless correct to assume that co-patents do result from some form of collaborative efforts. Belderbos et al. (2014) provide indications that co-patenting arrangements might mitigate ex-ante knowledge appropriation concerns, and potentially signal an intention by the entities to stay involved in further market exploitation efforts related to the underlying technology. As such, they reflect ‘joint’ or ‘open’ business strategies, offering a particular view into open business models and collaborative innovation activities.

Objectives

In this paper, we systematically map and analyse the extent to which co-patents (defined as patents owned jointly by two or more independent entities) signal a growing trend, in line with the rise of open business models and R&D collaborations.

To do so, we first address a methodological concern, where co-patenting numbers become inflated to the extent that different departments or subsidiaries of one and the same organization appear as distinct applicants on a patent application, which would signal internal patent filing strategies rather than R&D collaborations. This paper sets out by deflating co-patenting indicators accordingly.

Next, we use the deflated indicators of joint ownership to assess patterns of co-patenting activity for the period 1980-2015, whereby we consider all co-patent applications to the European Patent Office (EPO) originating from 43 European countries. In addition, by considering differences across sectors (involving companies, individuals, universities or governmental organizations) and across technological domains, we shed light on different configurations and their trends in collaborative R&D practices across European innovation systems.

Data & Methods

Deflating co-patent counts

To investigate the presence of co-ownership in patenting, data has been retrieved from the PATSTAT database (Autumn 2018 edition) for all patents filed with the EPO with priority years between 1978-2018 (European Patent Office, 2018). We start from the PATSTAT information on registered applicant(s) to distinguish single-filed patent applications (with one applicant) from jointly filed patent applications (with multiple applicants), identifying N=207,911 jointly filed patent applications with a total of N=362,253 applicant pairs.

Among those, we find indications of seeming co-applicant pairs, including ‘NOVARTIS AG’ patenting with ‘NOVARTIS-ERFINDUNGEN VERWALTUNGSGESELLSCHAFT M.B.H.’; the legal entity of ‘UNILEVER N.V’ in the Netherlands patenting with the legal entity ‘UNILEVER PLC’ in the United Kingdom; and ‘KONINKLIJKE PHILIPS ELECTRONICS N.V.’ patenting with different country-specific subsidiaries, such as ‘PHILIPS ELECTRONICS UK LIMITED’, ‘PHILIPS PATENTVERWALTUNG GMBH’, or ‘PHILIPS NORDEN AB’. This constitutes a problem if one is interested in the phenomenon of co-patenting as the involvement of multiple actors in R&D collaborations and as joint business strategies, rather than as an intra-organizational phenomena. The inclusion of such cases leads to an overestimation of the co-patenting phenomenon and accordingly to inflated co-patenting statistics.

To correct for this, we developed a name harmonisation approach that builds further upon the originally developed name harmonisation algorithm from KU Leuven (Van Looy, du Plessis, and Magerman 2006; Eurostat 2011), by considering the results of the removal of last common words (i.e. ‘COMPANY’, ‘TECHNOLOGY’ or ‘ELECTRONICS’) and a human rater case-by-case decision process on most frequently co-occurring applicant pairs or sharing the same first word. With our name harmonisation approach, we identified a total of 61,719 (non-unique) applicant pairs among all the jointly filed patent applications that in fact belong to the same (consolidated) organizational entity, whereas 216,496 applicant pairs represent truly independent entities. For the remaining set of 84,038 pairs, stratified sampling revealed no further possibilities to exclude potential ‘false positives’, based on the name harmonisation approach alone.

Turning to the level of co-owned patents, and focusing only on patent applications filed between 1980-2015 with at least one applicant from one of 43 European countries, Table 1 shows the difference between co-patent counts before and after removal of ‘false positives’ using the designed procedure. Out of the 117,868 jointly filed patent applications extracted from PATSTAT (2018 Autumn edition), 82,614 are identified as true co-patents. The remaining 35,254 pairs (30%) are identified as ‘false positives’.

Table 1. Number of co-patents before and after removal of false positives

	Co-Patents	Single-owned Patents	Total Patents	Co-patent shares (%)
Inflated	117,868	1,440,486	1,558,354	7.56
Deflated	82,614	1,475,740	1,558,354	5.30

In Figure 1, we present the deflated and inflated co-patent shares over time, revealing a systematic overestimation of the co-patenting phenomenon if ‘false positives’ are not corrected for.

Identification of co-patent trends

We use the *deflated* co-patent counts arising from the above-mentioned procedure, and explore the resulting patterns across sectors, fields and (European) countries. For sectors, we rely on the sector allocation results (Van Looy, du Plessis, and Magerman 2006; Eurostat 2011), for technology fields on the IPC patent classes and Technology Concordance Table, developed by the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI (Schmoch, 2008) and for countries on the categorization of their innovation typology in the European Commission’s Innovation Union Scoreboard (2015, i.e. the last year of data used in the study).

Figure 1. Inflated vs. deflated co-patent application shares

Results

Co-patenting trends across sectors, technology fields and countries

The time trend is disaggregated across sectors, as shown in Figure 2. While the share of co-patent applications involving a company (as a share of total patent applications filed by companies) remains stable at a comparatively low level of <5%, the relative share of co-patent applications filed by universities and governmental organizations displays a sharp increase, growing to around 44% for both sectors in 2015. As such, the relatively small variation in Figure 1 (~ 4,7-6%) is mainly the result of the stability of co-patenting shares among companies, which are responsible for the vast majority of patent applications.

The observed trends are further disentangled across co-patenting sector pairs. While the overall number of co-patent applications has grown considerably over time, this growth seems largely driven by sector pairs in which universities and governmental organizations – rather than companies – figure as co-owners. Indeed, the relative share of co-patent sector pairs (among all co-patents), show that the company-company combination has steadily decreased from around 41% in 1980 to 29% in 2015 (Figure 3). Similar decreasing trends can be observed for co-patents jointly filed by individuals, and – to a lesser extent – for company-individual combinations. Conversely, all combinations involving universities or governmental organizations have increased; most prominently for government-university co-patents, with a visible surge especially after the year 2000 (from 2% to 13% in 2015). Taken together, these trends show that the relative increase in co-patenting shares predominantly results from increased public sector involvement in co-ownership of patent applications.

As co-patenting trends might differ across technology fields, Figure 4 provides an overview of co-patent application shares by field. Comparatively high co-patenting shares are observed for Micro-structure and nano-technology (Technology Field 22), Analysis of biological materials (11), Biotechnology (15) and Pharmaceuticals (16). In particular, shares of co-patenting are higher and become more common over time in what can be considered the more science-intensive fields (Callaert et al., 2006).

Figure 2. Co-patent application shares within sectors

Figure 3. Co-patent application shares across sector pairs

Figure 4. Co-patent application shares by technology fields over time

Figure 5 shows the co-patenting shares within national patent portfolios across the different European innovation systems. The results suggest that countries with weaker innovation systems (including the moderate and modest innovators) have higher co-patenting shares.

Figure 5. Co-patent application shares by countries

The specificity of co-patenting trends

The country differences apparent in Figure 5 raise the question of whether the previously observed relative growth in co-patent shares (via increased relative public sector involvement and within science-intensive fields) are primarily signalling a developmental strategy within less developed innovation systems or whether the phenomenon is more generally valid, also among more developed innovation systems.

First, sectoral trends in co-patenting shares are disaggregated by the innovation performance of the country's innovation systems. Figure 6 shows that the previously observed increasing public sector involvement in co-patenting as well as the relatively stable private sector involvement (cf. Figure 2) apply to the different performance levels of country's innovation systems¹. Indeed, while innovation leaders may have lower levels of co-patenting and less outspoken growth in the public sectors, the trends are similar. For innovation followers and moderate innovators however, these trends are much more pronounced. The most striking increase in public sector co-patenting is observed among the innovation followers: from well below 20% in 1980 to over 60% by 2015.

Figure 6. Co-patent application shares by sectors and country's innovation typology

Second, Figure 7 further disentangles field effects in this respect. It reveals similar trends in co-patenting shares across fields, albeit again at different levels. The trends are most pronounced for the highlighted science-intensive fields (Micro-structure and nano-technology, Analysis of biological materials, Biotechnology, and Pharmaceuticals). Most consistently, these patterns are most outspoken among the innovation followers.

¹ Due to relatively low year-by-year patenting output among the modest innovators, these have been omitted.

Figure 7. Co-patent application shares by technology fields and innovation typologies

Third, to establish whether the increased public sector involvement only coincides with or whether it truly corresponds to higher co-patenting shares in the science-intensive fields, we developed a relative index that relates the number of co-patent sector combinations in a given technology field in a country to the size of the field in the technology portfolio of that same country. This relative index allows to conclude whether the occurrence of sector combinations is higher than could be expected given the field size. For each country we calculate:

$$\frac{\frac{\text{Number of sector-sector co-patents in Country X in Field Y}}{\sum \text{sector-sector co-patents in Country X}}}{\frac{\sum \text{patents in Country X in Field Y}}{\sum \text{patents in Country X}}} \quad (1)$$

We then take the mean of this number for each level of innovation performance (innovation leaders, innovation followers, moderate innovators). Finally, the index is normalized to become fitted within a range between 1 and -1, where > 0 indicates an occurrence of sector combinations that is higher than could be expected given the field size.

Figure 8 shows the distribution of this normalized index (for all cases >0) by technology fields. It reveals that both public-public and public-private co-patenting is much more pronounced and concentrated in those science-intensive fields where co-patenting has been a consistently growing trend. Interestingly, within the same fields, private-private co-patenting constellations are pronounced only among the innovation leaders, while private-private co-patenting among the innovation followers and moderate innovators are lower than what could

be expected considering the field's size in the country's technology portfolio². Moreover, the private-private co-patenting phenomenon is much more equitably distributed across fields.

Figure 8. Co-patent sector combination index by technology fields and innovation typology

Based on this, we propose that the increased public sector involvement truly corresponds to higher co-patenting shares, in particular within the highlighted science-intensive fields. This phenomenon occurs across all innovation systems, albeit at different levels of co-patenting shares and with the observable difference being the comparatively higher importance of also private-private efforts among the innovation leaders relative to the other countries.

Discussion & Conclusion

This study contributes with novel insights on the phenomena of joint ownership of patents. From a methodological point of view, we show the need to consolidate co-ownership of patents between independent entities by excluding apparent joint applications of one and the same entity. Our results reveal a considerable share of around 30% 'false positive' co-patents for a subset of patent applications originating from 43 European countries between 1980-2015.

From an empirical point of view, we map trends based on the deflated indicator, which indeed signal a growing importance of co-patenting as a tangible output of R&D collaborations, in particular since the mid-2000s, albeit with trends being highly differentiated across fields, countries and sectors. While we find that companies do not increase their (proportional) engagements in co-patenting practices, we observe sharp increases of co-patents among the patent portfolios of universities and governmental organizations. In general, besides being associated with public actors, higher co-patenting shares seem to occur relatively more in countries with less developed innovation systems. However, for some science-intensive

² With the exceptions of Biotechnology for the Innovation Followers and Analysis of biological materials for the Moderate Innovators.

fields, including pharmaceuticals, biotechnology and nanotechnology, we find similarly increasing co-ownership trends across all types of innovation systems, again predominantly involving actors of the public sphere.

We suggest that co-patent indicators may provide intriguing novel perspectives on the configurations of collaborative R&D practices across European innovation systems. Besides viewing co-patents as reflective of joint or open business strategies and observing that they become increasingly relevant in some constellations, our findings suggest that the presence of co-patents could signal developmental trajectories on the level of technological fields (science intensive fields) and on the level of (national) innovation systems (innovation followers and moderate innovators). Public actors seem to play a crucial role in these developmental trajectories.

Our observations are in line with the idea of differentiated value appropriation strategies of actors where co-patenting by companies is approached cautiously due to downward exploitation concerns resulting from shared intellectual property, which are of lesser concern among and with public actors (Belderbos et al., 2014). Yet another possibility is the supposed decline of science in corporate R&D where large companies have increasingly relied on externally generated knowledge from universities and smaller firms (Arora et al., 2017). Here, the observed trends where companies increasingly co-patent with universities or other governmental institutions, particularly in science-intensive fields might be signalling a trend whereby firms rely more systematically on development and commercialization of new knowledge generated in the public sector, especially when exploring novel fields.

To explore this further, we assessed correlations between the co-patent sector combination index across fields with the relative specialization (RTA) of academic, governmental, company and individual patents in those fields. Whereas the public-public and public-private co-patent index is very strongly positively correlated with relative specializations of the academic and governmental sector ($r \geq 0.84^{***}$), the private-private and public-private co-patent index is negatively correlated with relative specializations of company and individual patents ($r \leq -0.26^{***}$). This means that for public actors, co-ownership is aligned with their strengths, their relative specializations. For private actors, in contrast, co-ownership is situated in their under-specializations. Hence, these findings seem to suggest that firms strongly differentiate their (co-)ownership strategies depending on the nature of the innovative activity (exploitation versus exploration), and that (the evolution of) ownership strategies diverge sharply between private and public actors.

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